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In and Through Reason to Religion: An Exploration into the Relationship between Science and Religion

Kuruvilla Pandikattu, SJ

Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune 411014

Abstract: Based on the encyclical “Fides et Ratio” of Pope John Paul II, the author explores the relationship between reason and faith. The challenge before us to accept that “reason is valued without being overvalued.” Thus the precious reason that we possess must be cherished and should lead to its deeper dimension, that is faith. It is faith or religion that tries to deal with the deepest questions of human life. In this way, we need to go beyond reason by realising its own limitations and be critically open to the world of values, joy and hope. Finally, he holds that we by affirming and accepting the pandemic, we need to find hope and joy.

Keywords: Reason, Religion, Science, Faith, Relationship between Reason and Religion, Pandemic, Hope, Reality as Symbolic.

When we are ardently searching for corona vaccine and praying earnestly for it, it is worth reflecting on the intimate link between science and religion. In the context of belittling the scientific truth by religious fundamentalists, we need to reflect on the relationship between the two. I base my reflections on 1998 Encyclical “Fides et Ratio” of Pope John Paul II (FR 1998).

In the Encyclical he Pope recalls the admonition “know yourself” (*gnothi seauton*) carved on the temple portal at Delphi, as testimony to a basic truth that human beings may be

understood as those who seek to “know themselves”. As humans our basic challenge is to know ourselves. Unfortunately, we spend most of our life in exploring what others are, without asking the more fundamental questions about our own existence. Without taking the time to know ourselves and the world in and around us! Who am I? Where have I come from and where am I going? Why is there evil? What is there after this life? These perennial and fundamental questions were posed by the Bible, the Veda and the Avesta. They are found also in the writings of Confucius and Lao-Tze, in the preaching of Tirthankara and Buddha. The poetry of Homer and the tragedies of Euripides and Sophocles, as well as writings of Plato and Aristotle reflect on these questions (FR 1). After having explored the relationship between reason and faith or science and religion, we try to show that genuine faith can be attained only in and through reason. Without using reason, faith tends to become superstition. But if we do not move from reason to religion, by absolutizing religion, most of the noblest human experiences are also lost.

Philosophy as the Noblest Human Task

The Pope affirms passionately that Church is no stranger to this journey of discovery, nor could she ever be (FR 2). He avers that today we have at disposal an array of resources for generating greater knowledge of truth so that their lives may be ever more human. In this context philosophy (FR related to reason and science) emerges, then, as “one of noblest of human tasks” (FR 3). Born and nurtured when the human being first asked questions about the reason for things and their purpose, philosophy shows in different modes and forms that the desire for truth is part of human nature itself. It is an innate property of human reason to ask why things are as they are, even though the answers which gradually emerge are set within a horizon which reveals how the different human cultures are complementary (FR 3). There are genuine differences in our human situation, but they can also be brought together under the common umbrella of humanness. As human beings we have the

commonality of reason, which can facilitate encounter and engagement with each other.

The Church sees in philosophy the way to reach to fundamental truths about human life and considers “philosophy an indispensable help for a deeper understanding of faith and for communicating the truth of the Gospel” (FR 5). At the same time, the Pope also warns against “agnosticism and relativism which have led philosophical research to lose its way in the shifting sands of widespread scepticism.”

John Paul II is very clear that “there is thus no reason for competition of any kind between reason and faith: each contains the other, and each has its own scope for action.” He clearly acknowledges that faith is superior to reason (FR or philosophy or science). “But our vision of the face of God is always fragmentary and impaired by the limits of our understanding. Faith alone makes it possible to penetrate the mystery in a way that allows us to understand it coherently” (FR 13).

Here the Pope affirms that “reason is valued without being overvalued.” He elaborates: “The results of reasoning may in fact be true, but these results acquire their true meaning only if they are set within the larger horizon of faith” (FR 20). Thus reason is precious and it is valued. But we cannot absolutise reason and get struck there.

Humans as Seekers of Truth

We need to acknowledge that the search for truth is not always transparent nor does it always produce beneficial results. The natural limitation of reason and the inconstancy of the heart often obscure and distort a person's search. “Truth can also drown in a welter of other concerns. People can even run from the truth as soon as they glimpse it because they are afraid of its demands. Yet, for all that they may evade it, the truth still influences life (FR 28). Our life can never be permanently grounded upon doubt, uncertainty or deceit; such an existence would be threatened constantly by fear and anxiety. One may

“define” the human being, therefore, as the one who seeks the truth (FR 28).

The truths of philosophy, shared by scholars and ordinary people “shape a comprehensive vision and an answer to the question of life's meaning; and in the light of this they interpret their own life's course and regulate their behaviour.” (FR 30)

At this point, we may pose the question of the link between, on the one hand, the truths of philosophy and religion and, on the other, the truth revealed in Jesus Christ. But before tackling that question, one last datum of philosophy needs to be weighed. 30

Threefold Appeals

The Holy Father ends the Encyclical with separate appeals to theologians, philosophers, and scientists. It is quite significant that he addresses to these specific categories. It tells a lot about the priorities of the Church.

To theologians he says: “The intimate bond between theological and philosophical wisdom is one of the Christian tradition's most distinctive treasures in the exploration of revealed truth.” So he urges theologians “to recover and express to the full the metaphysical dimension of truth in order to enter into a demanding critical dialogue with both contemporary philosophical thought and with the philosophical tradition in all its aspects, whether consonant with the word of God or not.” He reminds them of Saint Bonaventure’s warning of “reading without repentance, knowledge without devotion, research without the impulse of wonder, prudence without the ability to surrender to joy, action divorced from religion, learning sundered from love, intelligence without humility, study sustained by divine grace, thought without the wisdom inspired by God” (Editorial Staff. n.d.).

He further invites the philosophers and particularly teachers of philosophy to “have the courage to recover, in the flow of an enduringly valid philosophical tradition, the range of authentic wisdom and truth – metaphysical truth included – which is proper to philosophical enquiry.” Philosophers are called to remain open “to the impelling questions which arise from the word of God and

they should be strong enough to shape their thought and discussion in response to that challenge” (FR 106).

Then he urges the scientists all over the world: “In expressing my admiration and in offering encouragement to these brave pioneers of scientific research, to whom humanity owes so much of its current development, I would urge them to continue their efforts without ever abandoning the *sapiential* horizon within which scientific and technological achievements are wedded to the philosophical and ethical values which are the distinctive and indelible mark of the human person” (FR 106). Finally, he asks *everyone* “to look more deeply at man, whom Christ has saved in the mystery of his love, and at the human being's unceasing search for truth and meaning” (FR 107). He extends the invitation to all human beings so that they can experience the deeper dimensions of truth and meaning in and through their normal daily lives.

In and Through Reason to Religion

In a way the Pope is urging us to embrace the religious the realm of faith in and through that of reason. We need to acknowledge our rational experience, from where comes philosophy and science. They are to be valued and cherished without absolutizing them. They should take us to the deeper level of faith and values.

One of the dangers of human lives is that we get stuck at the peripheral or empirical level. We become so absorbed in the things around us that we do not have the time to relish it. Here we tend to absolutise the world of senses and of reason (like positivism or scientism). We cannot allow science to be the arbitrator of everything else. Paul Kalanithi, the American neurologist, put it eloquently. “The problem, however, eventually became evident: to make science the arbiter of metaphysics is to banish not only God from the world but also love, hate, meaning — to consider a world that is self-evidently

not the world we live in. That's not to say that if you believe in meaning, you must also believe in God. It is to say, though, if you believe that science provides no basis for God, then you are almost obligated to conclude that science provides no basis for meaning and, therefore, life itself doesn't have any. In other words, existential claims have no weight; all knowledge is scientific knowledge" (Kalanithi 2016). Thus physics should lead to metaphysics!

Another extreme danger is that we think we can reach the Divine directly. We claim to experience God by our inner silence or mediation. This leads the temptation of not valuing the world and cherishing it. By denying the world and worldly experience we think that we can reach the depth of the world, i.e., the Divine. Thus metaphysics should be based on physics!

The middle way between these two extremes is to be open to the world around us (including reason) and go beyond it to the depth of reason itself. We can use reason to realise its own limits and thus make the "leap of faith," (Ogbonna 1997) which the Danish philosopher Kierkegaard invite us to do.

Kalanithi (2016) puts it powerfully: "Science may provide the most useful way to organize empirical, reproducible data, but its power to do so is predicated on its inability to grasp the most central aspects of human life: hope, fear, love, hate, beauty, envy, honor, weakness, striving, suffering, virtue." These central aspects of human life are dealt in religion, however imperfectly." Thus we need science. We cherish it. But in and through science we need to move to the deeper dimensions indicated by science, that of faith, commitment and depth.

This process can be better understood through the symbolic dimension of reality. Reality and reason are profoundly symbolic and they invite us to experience the depth of reality. The experience of the depth of reality or "surplus of meaning," (Ricoeur 2006) we are invited to embrace the whole reality and be open to further and deeper experiences (Pandikattu 2000). Thus, the challenge before us to cherish reason, realise its own limitations and go beyond it.

Thus, faith is not irrational. It is not antirational. It respects reason, values it, without overvaluing it. Understood thus it is in and through the material world that we reach the divine world. It is in and through reason that we reach faith.

Conclusion

In this pandemic situation we need to take seriously the work done by scientists, researchers and health workers in terms of healing and looking for an effective vaccine. We need to enable the spiritual leaders to heal with the trauma and tragedy caused by the pandemic at the personal and social level. The deeper problems of the evil of this pandemic and the lives lost or affected by this can only be properly answered by religion and spiritual openness. Thus truly we need science and technology. Very badly now. To heal our bodies. We also need the healing of our souls. To liberate ourselves from selfishness and greed. To accept death when it is necessary.

Thus the challenge facing us in these pandemic times is to go beyond it, without denying or bypassing it. By taking in the pain, suffering and the anxiety caused by the pandemic, can we still be beacons of hope? After being open to the tragedy and trauma of the death of thousands, can we still believe in ourselves and God? Can we find hope in and through this pandemic. That is the challenge facing us. That is liberative!

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Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ is the Dean, Faculty of Philosophy, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune. www.kuru.in Email: kuru@jdv.edu.in or kuru@kuru.in

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